

ISic2956

I.Sicily inscription 2956

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Morgantina

Place of origin (modern)

Morgantina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 32280

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331230

1. Διός.

2.

Edition: PHI336172

1. Διός.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645320

EDCS 70900985

PHI 331230

PHI 336172

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1315

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Manganaro, G. 1965. Per la storia dei culti in Sicilia. *Parola del Passato*. 20: 163-178. At 174 n.68

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 47 no.39 fig.114

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